

STRUCTURE, BUILDING, FUNCTIONS OF THE HISTORICAL CITY CENTER ON THE EXAMPLE OF DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCE

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«Reconstruction and restoration of architectural monuments»

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Abstract: The historical quarter occupies an important place in the planning structure of the city. It can be either an integral part of the historical center or an independent fragment of the urban environment. The most popular method for the reconstruction of a historical quarter in the historical center of the city is the rehabilitation of the territory, that is, the restoration of lost fragments of the surrounding landscape while preserving its original functional use or purpose. This technique is implemented differently in domestic and foreign practice.

Historic neighborhoods are becoming new citywide public spaces. They are assigned the role of cultural and educational centers. The historical quarter, as a rule, is integrated into the urban environment, has a developed pedestrian structure, which includes entertainment, sports, religious and recreational facilities, including those of citywide importance.

The article also presents the results of the first stage of scientific research aimed at solving one of the fundamental scientific problems of our time - the development of theoretical foundations and methods of conservation, restoration, regeneration and recreation of architectural and construction heritage in developing cities. The author proposes a theoretical basis for the formation of a new direction in architectural activity related to the neutralization and transformation of the destructive introduction of modern buildings into the historical environment of cities.

Key words: historical city center, historical quarter, historical buildings, cultural heritage sites, old and new architecture.

“Historical Quarter” is an urban formation that is a preserved fragment of historical buildings.

It can be located both in the central part of the city as part of the historical core, and beyond its borders. In the latter case, the historical quarter is an independent phenomenon, especially when the changes that took place in the planning structure of the city did not affect it. In particular, this is relevant if the historically established planning structure and perimeter line development have been preserved on the territory of the quarter and, at the same time, there are significant quantities of cultural heritage objects.

The formation of a “historical quarter” implies a large-scale restoration project within its urban planning boundaries and building area. Often it includes the reconstruction of all surviving buildings (complete reconstruction of the object according to old drawings). This approach is carried out with the aim of improving the quality and living conditions of the people inhabiting a given territory, the level of service for all citizens and the creation of an effective infrastructure focused on organic functioning in the citywide service system. Activities aimed at the reconstruction of “historic quarters” fulfill the task of preserving cultural heritage and at the same time improving the quality of the external urban environment.

In the conditions of reconstruction of the historical quarter, various methods of its implementation are distinguished - conservation, development, concentration of disparate functions, transfer of objects outside the historical quarter, demolition of dilapidated and low-value buildings, construction of new buildings [1].

It is worth highlighting the main list of methods for reconstructing the historical quarter in the historical center of the city:

- maintaining the space-planning structure of the quarter during the point-by-point restructuring of individual objects and improving the level of improvement;

- preservation of the existing structure and development of the historical quarter and careful inclusion into the space both in the central part and in the structure of its boundaries of new buildings, usually public

appointments;

- construction of new residential and public buildings in the historical quarter on the sites of demolished low-value buildings or those that have disappeared. The reception implies a radical reorganization of significant areas of historically developed areas of the city with a change in the functional purpose of objects used on the territory;

- rehabilitation of the territory, i.e. restoration of lost fragments of the historical landscape while maintaining its functional purpose.

An analysis of modern design practice has shown that the most common is a complex reconstruction of a historical territory, which implies the regeneration of the historically developed environment as part of its planning structure, functional areas, buildings and historical landscape. This technique is carried out with the aim of reviving certain urban spaces in a social and economic sense. As a rule, lost historical buildings are recreated, as mentioned above, using surviving drawings [2].

Preservation of the structure of the quarter during spot reconstruction of individual objects and improvement of landscaping. Such events are held on the territory where cultural heritage sites are located. That is why, when reconstructing individual buildings within the boundaries of the historical quarter, the following principles are observed: limiting the height of the objects being rebuilt (the maximum height of the existing building is taken as a guide), combining the historical shell and modern content in a single building, forming a modern cultural business center within the historically established boundaries of the quarter [3]. Construction work is carried out both at the expense of the state and at the expense of funds raised from private investors. A successful example of the rehabilitation of the territory of a historical quarter, aimed at restoring lost fragments of the surrounding landscape while maintaining functional use.

Preservation of the structure and development of the historical quarter and the formation of complexes of new public buildings in the central area or near its borders. This option is especially popular in foreign urban planning and involves the construction of buildings that are new in architecture and function while maintaining the main typological characteristics of the old buildings and the historical street grid. Development of the territory is carried out strictly in accordance with the regulations developed for these activities. They involve limiting the height of the house being built, maintaining the height of the eaves of all buildings at the same level as neighboring old houses, and using stone for cladding the facade. As a result, an ordinary block of historically valuable buildings retained its original urban planning scale and, at the same time, in accordance with the requirements of the time, received a new functional meaning.

Construction of new residential and public buildings in the historical quarter on the site of demolished low-value buildings. This technique implies a radical reorganization of large areas of the city with a change in the functional use of the territory [4].

Rehabilitation of the territory, i.e. restoration of lost fragments of the historical landscape while maintaining the original functional purpose. In this case, the activities are aimed at preserving, restoring, and transferring surviving cultural heritage objects from various areas of the city to the territory of the historical quarter in order to recreate the historical architectural and spatial environment and fill it with new functions. This technique is typical for neighborhoods whose territory coincides with the territory of the historical center of the city. As a rule, such neighborhoods have a planning structure laid down in the first master plans. The formation of the development of these quarters is carried out on the basis of the historical general plan. Moreover, all work is carried out both at the expense of the state and at the expense of private investors.

Analysis of the studied material showed that in practical design, when reconstructing a historical quarter, the method of complete rehabilitation of the

territory is most often used. It involves the restoration of lost fragments of the surrounding landscape while maintaining functional use or purpose [5].

In foreign practice, the restoration of historical neighborhoods includes the following positions: restoration of existing buildings, restoration of lost objects according to surviving drawings, or construction of new buildings, the architecture of which has retained the main typological characteristics of the old buildings and the historical street grid. Thus, historical quarters abroad are multifunctional quarters that are as close as possible to the historical original.

In domestic urban planning, the historical quarter consists mainly of residential buildings of the old period. It is made according to one of the types: estate, where residential buildings are located inside the property, where residential buildings form a perimeter row development of blocks. Currently, the basis of the historical quarter is made up of pakhsa buildings or adobe bricks, its preservation and restoration is carried out in compliance with a number of principles: restoration of existing and construction of lost cultural heritage sites, transfer of cultural heritage sites from other parts of the city. Practice has shown that complex reconstruction is most often used in our country, which includes complete regeneration of the historical environment.

Thus, we can conclude that in Uzbekistan, historical neighborhoods are becoming new citywide public spaces. They are assigned the role of cultural and educational centers. The historical quarter, as a rule, is integrated into the urban environment, has a developed pedestrian structure, which includes entertainment, sports, religious and recreational facilities, including those of citywide importance. Here there are organized walking routes that provide spatial connections between the main groups of monuments [6].

Another thing is that, unlike the situation abroad, in Uzbekistan the percentage of loss of national architectural monuments is small and decreases every year. The preservation of historical buildings and the reconstruction of architectural monuments require constant attention from both government officials and design professionals.

Bibliography

1. Barkhin, M. G. City, structure and composition / M. G. Barkhin. - Moscow : Science, 1984. – 264 p. – Text: direct.
2. Korotich, M. A. Traditional and modern forms in architecture: the problem of interaction / M. A. Korotich. – Text: direct // Academic bulletin UralNIIProekt RAASN. – 2010. – No. 2. – P. 61-63.
3. Leizerova, A.V. Traditional street as an integral urban planning structure tour / A. V. Leizerova. – Text: direct // Architect: news of universities. 2019. – No. 1(65). – P. 1-15.
4. Zubaydullaev, U. Z. (2023). STUDY OF THE PREPARATION OF TRAINING OF ARCHITECTURE STUDENTS IN EDUCATIONAL PRACTICE IN THE SYSTEM OF HIGHER EDUCATION. JOURNAL OF

ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE, 818-824.

5. Architectural monuments of Central Asia. Bukhara, Samarkand: Photo album/ Author of text and compositions. V.L.Voronina. -L.: Aurora, 1969. 39 f., 44 l. -L.: Aurora, 1969. - Text paral. rus., engl.

6. Ziyadullayevich, Z. U. (2023). DECOR IN CONTEMPORARY ARCHITECTURE IN CENTRAL ASIA-TRADITIONS AND INNOVATIONS. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF ARTS AND DESIGN, 198-204.

7. Farangiz, K., & Siroj, T. (2024). STAGES OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF SHAHRISABZ CITY. Synergy: Cross-Disciplinary Journal of Digital Investigation (2995-4827), 2(4), 16-20

8. Zubaydullayev, U. Z., & Asrorov, O. A. (2021). The relevance of creating a system of underground parking in the historical centers of central asian cities on the example of the city of Samarkand. Asian Journal Of Multidimensional Research, 10(7), 145-149.

9. Зубайдуллаев, У. З., Мирзаев, Д. М., & Маматова, С. (2018). ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КУЛЬТУРНОГО ЛАНДШАФТА В ПРОЦЕССЕ УРБАНИЗАЦИИ. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире, (4-12), 38-41.

10. Farangiz, K. (2023). WAYS OF FORMING AND DEVELOPING COMMUNITY CENTERS. JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE, 280-284.

